

Adsorption of Long Chain Ions and their Surface Pressure at Oil/Water Interface

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Some of the equations proposed for the adsorption of long chain ions at oil/water interface have been critically discussed and it has been pointed out that mutual electrostatic repulsion of the long chain ions at the interface is not the limiting factor in their adsorption, consequently the constants in the Langmuir adsorption isotherm do not change with the increase or decrease in the adsorption of the long chain ions and for a given ionic strength $K_1 \exp. (w-ze.\Psi_o)/kT$ has got a definite value. Experimental data in support of Langmuir adsorption isotherm have been cited. It has also been suggested that adsorption measured by analytical methods is more accurate than that measured by the surface tension method.

The extent of validity of some of the equations proposed to account for the pressure-area relationship of the adsorbed ions at oil/water interface has been tested using reliable experimental data. It has been shown that for dodecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide the data fit the equation of Ghosh better than those proposed by Davies and by Phillips and Rideal. To take into consideration the effect of added salt, a slight modification of Ghosh's equation has been suggested.

1. (a) *Analysis of the equations proposed for adsorption :*

In a previous paper¹, it has been shown by one of us that Langmuir's theory of adsorption may be extended to oil/water interface and an equation can be derived connecting the lateral pressure π with the area A occupied by an adsorbed long chain ion. This equation has been found to agree well with the data obtained by Cockbain² using sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaDS) at n -decane/water interface.

There is, considerable difference of opinion regarding the applicability of Langmuir equation to the adsorption of detergent ions at the air/water or oil/water interface. It has been pointed out that electrical repulsion due to the charged heads of the adsorbed long chain ions will retard their further adsorption specially when the area A occupied by such an ion at the interface is small. Several authors^{3,4} have, therefore, proposed modified equations in which the effect of this electrostatic repulsion has been taken into consideration. Davies³ has proposed the following equation;—

$$n = \frac{(B_1/B_2) C \exp (W-Ze \Psi_o)/kT}{1 + (B_1/B_2 n_o) C \exp (W-Ze \Psi_o)/kT} \quad \dots (1)$$

where n and n_o represent the number of ions adsorbed per 1 cm^2 of the interface at a concentration C and at adsorption saturation respectively, B_1 and B_2 are constants, W is the energy of interaction of the long chain containing CH_2 groups with the oil, Z the valency of the detergent ion, Ψ_o the difference of potential between the plane CD (vide Fig. 1(a) passing through the centres of the ionic heads and the interior of the solution and the other terms have their usual significance.

1. B. N. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **43**, 19.
2. E. G. Cockbain, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 874.
3. J. T. Davies, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1958, A245, 417, 429; *Interfacial phenomena* by Davies and Rideal, 2nd Ed. Academic Press, New York and London, 1963. p. 186.
4. R. C. Groot, Thesis (University of Utrecht)-1965, pp. 16-18.

If $(B_1/B_2 n_o)$ be put equal to k_1 , then equation (1) assumes the form

$$n = \frac{n_o k_1 C \exp^{(W-Ze\Psi_o)/kT}}{1+k_1 C \exp^{(W-Ze\Psi_o)/kT}} \quad \dots \quad (1.a)$$

which differs from the Langmuir equation in containing the term $\exp^{(W-Ze\Psi_o)/kT}$.

FIG. 1

Equation (1.a) can also be expressed in the form

$$\frac{n}{n_o - n} = k_1 C \exp^{(W - Ze\Psi_o)/kT} \quad \dots \quad (1.b)$$

Groot⁴ has shown that when $\Psi_o > 100$ m.V. and $Z=1$, one can put $\exp^{-Ze\Psi_o}/kT = a \text{ constant} \times C_1/n^2$ where C_1 is the total electrolyte concentration in the interior of the solution. Equation (1b) under this condition can be written as

$$\frac{C_1 C}{n^3} = \frac{C_1 C}{n_o n^2} + a \text{ constant} \quad \dots \quad (1.c)$$

when the solution contains only detergent ions then $C_1 = C$ and equation (1.c) assumes the form

$$\frac{C^2}{n^3} = \frac{C^2}{n_o n^2} + a \text{ constant} \quad \dots \quad (1.d)$$

It has been reported by Groot⁴ that equations (1.c) and (1.d) agree well with his experimental data on adsorption of (NaDS) at Nujol/water interface.

It is to be noted that the equations (1) to (1d) are based on the assumption that electrostatic repulsion between the charged heads of the long chain ions is the limiting factor in determining their adsorption per unit area. Davies assumes that the centres of the heads of the adsorbed ions all lie in a plane CD which is at a distance of about 3 \AA below the oil/water interface AB (vide Fig. 1(a)). According to Gibbs theory the adsorbed layer should as a whole be electrically neutral. In the case of long chain ions containing say, 12 or more CH_2 groups, the thickness of the adsorbed layer must, therefore, be more than 18 \AA extending from plane AB to plane EF say, and a long chain ion such as H (Fig. 1(a)) should be considered as adsorbed. The electrical work

involved in its adsorption is much less than $Ze\psi_0$ since the charged head is at a level where the potential is much less than ψ_0 . On the basis of Boltzmann's distribution law, it is quite probable that the charged heads of the long chain ions will lie at different distances from the interface AB as depicted qualitatively in Fig. 1(b).

If $7 \times 10^{-3}M$ represents the concentration in bulk of a solution of a strong ionic detergent containing 12 CH_2 groups in the long chain then its concentration at n-decane/water interface at 20° , according to Boltzmann's distribution law[†], should be as high as $28M$ (approximately) taking $W=12 \times 810$ calories, $Z=1$ and $\psi_0=210$ mV. For sodium lauryl sulphate (NaDS) on n-decane/water interface at adsorption saturation, Cockbain² has found that the area per long chain ion is about 42 \AA^2 . Taking the thickness of the adsorbed layer as small as 5 \AA , the concentration of the ions near the interface is found to be $8.3M$ only and this is much less than that viz. $28 M$ found on the basis of the Boltzmann distribution law taking the repulsion of the charged heads into consideration. Hence the limiting factor for the adsorption of detergent ions containing 12 or more CH_2 groups in the long chain at oil/water interface is not the electrostatic repulsion of the charged heads. It is either the physical capacity of unit area of the interface to accommodate the detergent ions or their solubility in the pair of liquids selected that constitutes the limiting factor. The term $\exp(W-Ze\psi_0)/kT$ in equation (1) should, therefore, be treated as a constant with a value consistent with the restrictive conditions prevailing at the interface. Equation (1.a) can then be written with a constant K as follows

$$n = \frac{n_0 KC}{1 + KC} \quad \dots \quad (1.e)$$

Equation (1.e) is of the same form as the Langmuir adsorption isotherm.

1. (b) *Experimental test of equation (1.e):*

For experimental verification it is convenient to express equation (1.e) in the following form

$$\frac{1}{n} = \frac{1}{n_0 KC} + \frac{1}{n_0} \quad \dots \quad (1.f)$$

Vold and Groot⁵ have reported that their data on the adsorption of (NaDS) at Nujol/water interface agree well with the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. Emulsions having a given volume ratio of Nujol and water have been prepared using different concentrations of (NaDS). The concentration of (NaDS) in water, before and after dispersion of Nujol, has been determined in each case by titration with a pure cationic surfactant (Cetyl-pyridinium bromide).

Groot's⁴ data are represented in Fig. 2 in which n has been expressed in moles of (NaDS) adsorbed per ml. of Nujol dispersed and C, the concentration of (NaDS) in moles

[†]Modification of Boltzmann's equation by introducing space restriction for ionic volumes has been attempted by several authors such as Bickerman. (*Phil. Mag.*, 1942, **33**, 384); G. M. Bell and S. Levine (*Proc. 2nd Inter Congr. Surf. Activity* (1957, **3**, 125); D. A. Haydon and F. H. Taylor (*Phil. Trans.* 1960, A 253, 255).

5. R. D. Vold and R. C. Groot—*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 1969.

per litre. It will be noticed that the plot of $1/n$ against $1/C$ is linear as is to be expected from equation (1.f). Groot⁴ reported slight difference in the values of n_0 observed in the presence and absence of NaCl in the solution. This difference may be caused by the adsorption of a few micelles, the formation of which is helped by NaCl in the region of relatively high concentration of (NaDS) used by him.

The adsorption of (NaDS) at n-decane/water interface has been measured by Cockbain² using the emulsion technique. Given volumes of n-decane and water containing different concentrations of (NaDS) have been emulsified and the concentration of (NaDS) in water, before and after emulsification has been determined by titration with a cationic surfactant. The number of (NaDS) ions adsorbed per Cm^2 of the interface has also been found by him, using Gibb's isotherm and data on interfacial tension measurement. In Fig. 3a are plotted the data of Cockbain obtained by the titration method. A represents the area in $(\text{\AA})^2$ per ion and C the concentration of (NaDS) in moles per litre. Since $1/n = A$, it will be noticed from Fig. 3a that the relation between $1/n$ and $1/C$ is linear in agreement with equation (1.f).

Haydon and Phillips⁶ have estimated the adsorption of dodecyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide (DTAB) at petroleum ether/water interface from measurements of surface potential. Their data have been plotted in Fig. 3b in which A represents the area per ion in $(\text{\AA})^2$ and C the concentration of (DTAB) in moles per litre. It will be noticed that the relation between A (i.e. $1/n$) and $1/C$ is linear in satisfactory agreement with equation (1.f).

Using Gibb's equation in the form, $n = 2/RT \, d\gamma/d\ln C$ and data on measurement of interfacial tension, Haydon and Phillips⁶ have also calculated the adsorption of (DTAB) at petroleum ether/water interface. These adsorption data are represented in Fig. 3b by + marks. It will be noticed that some of the points indicate much smaller values of adsorption than those found from measurement of surface potential. Similar difference in the values of adsorption calculated from Gibb's equation and surface tension data and those determined by purely analytical method is also noticeable in the case of (NaDS) investigated by Cockbain². It is, therefore, to be noted that the limits of error in the value of adsorption found from Gibb's equation and interfacial tension measurement are much greater than that found by analytical and other methods. In this connection it may be pointed out that depending on the slope, a small error in drawing the $\gamma - \log C$, curve and the tangent to it at a given point may produce a relatively large error in the value of adsorption calculated by using Gibb's equation. One should, therefore, be very cautious in drawing conclusions from data on adsorption determined by surface tension method alone.

Adsorption of pure (NaDS)⁺ at n-heptane/water interface has also been measured by using the emulsion technique. Heptane and water in a given volume ratio, have been emulsified by shaking in stoppered bottles in the absence of air using different concentrations of (NaDS) at a constant ionic strength of 0.01 maintained with NaCl. The emulsion is then passed through a hand operated homogenizer and allowed to stand until a clear aqueous layer separated from the lower end of the bottle. A portion of the clear solution is carefully withdrawn and analysed by titration with a pure cationic surfactant. The results obtained are represented in Fig. 4 in which n represents moles of (NaDS) adsorbed

6. D. A. Haydon and J. N. Phillips. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, **54**, 698.

*The sample of pure (NaDS) was a kind gift of Professor K. J. Mysels,

by 10 ml. of n-heptane dispersed, C the concentration of (NaDS) in moles per litre and f, the mean activity coefficient of the ions in the solution of ionic strength 0.01. It will be noticed that the relation between $1/n$ and $1/Cf$ is linear as is to be expected from equation (1.f). It may, therefore, be concluded that within the range of concentrations investigated and recorded above, adsorption of (NaDS) and (DTAB) at oil/water interface can be satisfactorily represented by the Langmuir adsorption isotherm.

FIG. 3

Fig. 4. n = moles adsorbed by 10 ml of dispersed heptane in water.
 C = con. in moles/litre f = activity coefficient at ionic strength 0.01.

Some of the equations proposed for the lateral pressure exerted by long chain ions at oil/water interface and their range of validity.

According to Ghosh¹, the lateral pressure π exerted by long chain ions at oil/water interface may be represented by the equation

$$\pi = 2 \pi_0 + \Delta \pi = 2 n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A - A_0} \right) + \pi_0 \left(\frac{A - A_0}{A} \right) f \quad \dots \quad (1.g)$$

$$= 2 n_0 kT \left(1 + f \frac{A - A_0}{2A} \right) \ln \frac{A}{A - A_0} \quad \dots \quad (1.h)$$

in which each of the ionic species (i.e. the adsorbed long chain ions and their counter ions) exerts the pressure π_0 and $\Delta\pi$ is the additional pressure caused by the mutual electrostatic repulsion of the charged heads of the long chain ions. For $\Delta\pi$ he has derived the expression $\pi_0 (A - A_0)/A$ and has multiplied it by f , a factor related to the mean activity coefficient of the ions, to account for the effect of ionic strength of the solution on inter-ionic attraction. A correction for this effect may also be introduced from a consideration of the free energy, per unit area, of the electrical double layer in the same way as has been done by Davies⁷. On the basis of such consideration it appears that $\Delta\pi$ should be smaller than $(kT/A - 6.1\sqrt{C})$. Therefore, it has been assumed that $\Delta\pi = (kT/2A) (1 + [A - A_0]/A) - 6.1\sqrt{C}$, approximately. In the aforesaid calculation of free energy the effect of finite size of the ions has not been taken into consideration. When this is done, $6.1\sqrt{C}/(1 + Ba\sqrt{C})$ should be used in place of $6.1\sqrt{C}$. Introducing this value of $\Delta\pi$ in equation (1.g) of Ghosh and taking $Ba = 1$ approximately⁸, it may be written as

$$\pi = 2n_0 kT \ln \left(\frac{A}{A - A_0} \right) + \frac{kT}{2A} \left(1 + \frac{A - A_0}{A} \right) - \frac{6.1\sqrt{C}}{1 + \sqrt{C}} \quad \dots \quad (1.i)$$

It may also be pointed out that f in equation (1.h) of Ghosh may be dropped and it may be expressed as follows

$$\pi = 2n_0 kT \left(1 + \frac{A - A_0}{2A} \right) \ln \left(\frac{A}{A - A_0} \right) - \frac{6.1\sqrt{C}}{1 + \sqrt{C}} \quad \dots \quad (1.k)$$

The values of π calculated from the equations (1.h) and (1.k) are not likely to differ much from one another.

Davies⁷ has derived for oil/water interface the following equation which is fairly widely known

$$\pi = \frac{kT}{A - A_0} + 6.1\sqrt{C} \left[\text{Cosh Sinh}^{-1} \left(\frac{134}{A\sqrt{C}} \right) - 1 \right] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

When $A\sqrt{C} < 38$, this equation reduces to

$$\pi = \frac{3 kT}{A - A_0} - 6.1\sqrt{C} - \frac{2 kTA_0}{A(A - A_0)} \quad \dots \quad (2.a)$$

Some doubt has been expressed regarding the applicability of equation (2) of Davies to

⁷ J. T. Davies—*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1951, **A208**, 224.

⁸ B is a constant 3.3×10^7 for water and 'a' the average effective diameter of the ions (vide "Electrochemistry" by Glasstone 1937, p. 142.)

solutions containing no added electrolyte. Phillips and Rideal have, therefore, proposed the following equation

$$\pi = \frac{2kT}{A - A_0} + 6.1\sqrt{C} \left[\text{Cosh Sinh}^{-1} \left(\frac{134}{A\sqrt{C}} \right) - 1 \right] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) differs from equation (2) of Davies only by the factor 2 by which $kT/(A - A_0)$ has been multiplied. Equation (3) as Haydon⁹ points out can also be written in the following form without introducing any appreciable error

$$\pi = \frac{2kT}{A - A_0} + 6.1\sqrt{C} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{134}{A\sqrt{C}} \right)^2} - 1 \right] \quad \dots \quad (3.a)$$

Experimental test of the aforesaid equations :

In table I are recorded the data taken from Fig. 15 of the paper of Davies⁷ for the system $C_{26}H_{53}N(CH_3)_3^+$ at oil/water interface in the presence of $10^{-3}N, NaCl$. Since the ionic strength is low, equation (1.h) of Ghosh has been used for this system. Column—IV of Table I contains values of π calculated from equation (2.a) of Davies using $A_0 = 30(\text{\AA})^2$ chosen by him, while column III contains those calculated from the equation (1.h) of Ghosh taking $f=1$ and $A_0 = 40(\text{\AA})^2$. This choice of $A_0 = 40(\text{\AA})^2$ is due to the fact that no experimental value of A_0 at adsorption saturation of $C_{26}H_{53}N(CH_3)_3^+$ is available and that for (NaDS) Cockbain found a value of A_0 nearly equal to $40(\text{\AA})^2$ at oil/water interface.

In table II are recorded the data of Haydon and Phillips⁶ on dodecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (DTAB) at petroleum ether/water interface, A being found from surface potential measurement. Column IV of the Table contains values of π calculated from equation (2.a) of Davies taking $A_0 = 30(\text{\AA})^2$ which fits the data best, column V contains the values of π calculated from equation (3.a) of Phillips and Rideal taking $A_0 = 25(\text{\AA})^2$ which gives the best fit and column VI contains the values of π calculated from equation (1.h) of Ghosh taking $A_0 = 55.4(\text{\AA})^2$ and $f=1$. The reason for choosing $A_0 = 55.4(\text{\AA})^2$ is that a plot of $1/n$ against $1/C$ gives a linear relation according to the adsorption isotherm (1.f) and from the extrapolation of the line the aforesaid value of A_0 is obtained. Equation (1.h) of Ghosh has been used since there is no added electrolyte and (DTAB) concentration is very small.

In Table III are recorded, after necessary numerical calculations, the data taken from Table IV of the paper of Davies⁷. Columns 6, 7, 8 of Table III contain the values of π calculated from the equations (2.a) and (1.i) and (1.k) of Davies and the authors respectively. The value of A_0 used in the equations (1.i) and (1.k) is $40(\text{\AA})^2$ for each of the three substances.

TABLE I

*Monolayers of C₂₆H₅₃N(CH₃)₃⁺ at oil/water interface.*Value of A₀ used in equation 2a of Davies = 30(Å)²,, ,, ,, ,, ,, (1.h) of Ghosh=40(Å)²

Area per ion (Å)	π in dynes observed	π in dynes calculated from			π in dynes observed	π in dynes calculated from	
		Equ ⁿ (2a) of Davies	Equ ⁿ (1.h) of Ghosh	A area per ion in (Å) ²		Eq ⁿ (2a) of Davies	Eq ⁿ (1.h) of Ghosh
69.0	20.7	22.0	21.2	226.0	5.0	5.6	5.5
83.4	16.27 16.2	18.2	16.6	345.0	2.9 2.8	3.4	3.6
91.7	13.5	15.2	14.8	693.0	1.5 1.7	1.6	1.8
113.0	11.2	11.9	11.7	923.0	1.2	1.1	1.3
137.0	8.0	9.9	9.3	1381.0	0.7	0.7	0.9
135.0	8.7	8.3	8.4	1385	0.8	0.7	0.9
193	7.2 5.8	6.5	6.6		0.9		

TABLE II

*Monolayers of Dodecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (DTAB) at oil/water interface.*Value of A₀ used in equation (2a) of Davies=30(Å)²,, ,, ,, ,, ,, (3a) of Phillips and Rideal=25(Å)²,, ,, ,, ,, ,, ,, (1.h) of Ghosh=55.4(Å)²

C Con in mole	A Area per ion in (Å) ²	π in dynes observed	π in dynes calculated from		
			Equation (2a) of Davies	Equation (3a) of Phillips & Rideal	Equation (1.h) of Ghosh
0.0158	†(58.1)	44.7			46.3
0.0100	60	39.5	26.6	36.3	40.5
0.00631	63.7	33.5	24.4	33.4	32.0
0.00398	67.8	28.0	22.5	30.5	27.3
0.00251	76.0	23.0	19.3	26.3	21.7
0.00158	85.0	19.0	16.8	22.8	18.2
0.00100	103.0	15.5	13.3	18.1	14.0
0.00063	132.0	12.5	10.1	13.7	10.3

TABLE III

Substance	Ionic strength	A per ion in (Å) ²	A ₀ used in eq ⁿ (2) of Davies	π in dynes observed	π in dynes calculated from		
					Eq ⁿ (2a) of Davies	Eq ⁿ (1.i)	Eq ⁿ (1.k)
Cetyl Sulphate	0.01	380	20	2.0	2.7	2.7	2.7
C ₂₆ D ₅₃ N(CH ₃) ₃ ⁺	0.001	690	30	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.6
α-zamino-palmitic acid pH=1.7	0.1	120	30	9.0	9.4	9.6	9.5

† This value of A was taken from the graph in Fig. 3 (b).

DISCUSSION

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I, that the values of π calculated from equation (1.h) of Ghosh are quite close to those calculated from equation (2a) of Davies. There is hardly any difference in the values of π calculated from the two equations. The agreement between the observed and calculated values of π is also fairly satisfactory.

From the data recorded in Table II it is evident that equation (3.a) of Davies yields an appreciably low value of π throughout compared with the observed values. The equation (3.a) of Rideal yields a high value of π all along except the first two. The values of π calculated from equation (1. h) of Ghosh agree fairly with those observed except the last one (corresponding to the concentration 0.00063 of the detergent) where π calculated is appreciably less than π observed.

From the data recorded in Table III it appears that the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of π is fair. Equation (2 a) of Davies and (1.i) and (1.k) of the authors give almost the same values of π .

It may be mentioned that a number of equations, other than those discussed above, have been proposed by different authors to account for the relationship between π and A at the oil/water and air/water interface. It would be worthwhile considering critically the merits and defects of these equations with a view to arrive at a relatively more satisfactory solution of the problem.

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